

1 **EXPERIMENTAL DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF LOW-COST SCALABLE**
2 **RADIATIVE COOLING MATERIALS FOR BUILDING APPLICATIONS**

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21 **HIGHLIGHTS**

22 Design, optimization, fabrication, characterization, and testing of daytime radiative
23 cooling materials.

24 Low-cost scalable spray-coating technique for built-environment application.

25 Materials tested under unfavorable meteorological conditions.

26 Samples were a maximum of 7.32 °C below ambient during the day and 9.13 °C night.

27 Emissive coat costs 0.3 €/m² for a 2 μm layer of polymethylsilsesquioxane with SiO₂
28 nanoparticles.

29

30 **ABSTRACT**

31 Urban overheating has a serious impact on building energy consumption. Daytime
32 radiative cooling materials are an interesting passive solution for refrigeration.

33 However, their costs and applications hinder their current application. In this study, a
34 series of scalable and lowcost daytime radiative cooling (DTRC) materials were

35 designed, fabricated, and tested in a moderate climate (Cfb-Köppen-Geiger

36 classification) and compared to aluminum and Vikuiti. The methodology was: i) material
37 selection and design, (ii) optimization, (iii) fabrication, (iv) characterization, and (v)

38 testing. The materials were fabricated using different substrates, aluminum and Vikuiti,

39 and two kinds of formulations for the emissive layers based on silica-derived polymer

40 polymethylsilsesquioxane (PMSQ) with embedded silica nanoparticles. The resulting

41 aluminum DTRC materials had a mean solar reflectivity of 0.7 and 0.34 emissivity in

42 the atmospheric window, the samples with Vikuiti had 0.97 and 0.89, respectively.

43 During the experiment, the samples were exposed to different ambient conditions

44 without a convection barrier and were contained in an extruded polystyrene board to

45 eliminate conduction. The samples reached 7.32 °C and 9.13 °C maximum surface

46 temperature reduction (below ambient) during the day and night, respectively. The

47 samples with the commercial substrate achieved a mean reduction of 3.72 °C below
48 ambient temperature. Although the aluminum samples did not achieve subambient
49 cooling throughout the entire day, the emissive layer reduced the sample's surface
50 temperature by an average of 1.7 °C. The PMSQ radiative cooling materials show
51 great potential for future building applications. Suitability under different climates and
52 experimental settings should be done to test broad applicability.

53 **KEYWORDS**

54 Daytime radiative cooling; spectrally selective materials; scalable material
55 development; subambient cooling; spray coating deposition

56

57 **1. Introduction**

58 Urban heat islands are the most documented phenomena of climate change. Urban
59 overheating is associated with higher urban temperatures in the dense parts of the
60 cities compared to the surrounding suburban or rural areas [1]. Overheating sources
61 include the released anthropogenic heat, high absorption of solar radiation by the
62 urban materials and structures, decreased airflow and urban ventilation, reduced
63 evapotranspiration, and limited radiative losses [2]. The phenomenon is documented in
64 more than 400 cities worldwide; the amplitude of urban overheating may range
65 between 1 to 10 °C averaging 5 to 6 °C [3]. Synergies with the global climate change
66 and heat waves further intensify the amplitude of urban overheating [4].

67 Urban overheating has a serious impact on the cooling energy consumption of
68 buildings, outdoor pollution levels, heat related mortality and morbidity, urban
69 ecological footprint and survivability levels [5]. It is reported that urban overheating
70 rises the peak electricity load varies between 0.45% and 4.6%, equivalent to an
71 electricity penalty of about 21 (± 10.4) W per degree of temperature increase and per
72 person [6]. Moreover, the additional energy penalty induced by urban overheating is

73 close to 0.74 kWh/m²/C, while the Global Energy Penalty per person is close to
74 237,(±130) kWh/p [7]. In parallel, recent research has found that populations living in
75 cities' with warmer precincts have a close to 6% higher risk of mortality than those
76 living in cooler urban neighborhoods [8].

77 To counterbalance the impact of urban overheating, several mitigation technologies
78 have been proposed and implemented in cities. Proposed technologies include
79 reflective and chromic materials for the urban fabric, additional green infrastructure,
80 evaporative systems, solar control devices, and the use of low temperature heat sinks
81 [3]. Implementation of the proposed mitigation technologies in large scale projects
82 showed that it is possible to decrease the peak temperature of cities up to 2.5-3 °C [9].
83 Among the various proposed technologies, the use of reflective, thermochromic, and
84 photonic materials seems to present the highest mitigation potential [10]. Recent data
85 have shown that the use of reflective materials in cities reduces the ambient
86 temperature by 0.09 °C per 0.1 increase of the urban albedo while reducing heat
87 related mortality between 0.1 to 4 deaths per day [11].

88 The recent development of photonic and plasmonic materials has skyrocketed the
89 mitigation potential of modern materials used in the built environment. Photonic
90 materials or Daytime Radiative Coolers (DTRC) exhibit subambient surface
91 temperatures during the daytime under the sun [12].

92 Daytime radiative cooling materials can be classified into multilayer photonic structures,
93 metamaterial 2D-3D photonic structures, polymers, and paints for radiative cooling [12].
94 Although other materials had previously achieved daytime radiative cooling, a new
95 photonic material recently achieved 4 °C below ambient temperature under direct
96 sunlight [13]. This photonic material was a breakthrough in the field, and many authors
97 have followed their approach. Numerical simulation of the sample inside a vacuum
98 chamber showed a theoretical maximum reduction of 60 °C [14] below ambient
99 temperature. Experimentally, the material achieved an average temperature reduction

100 of 37.4 °C with a sunblock. A double-layer coating composed of densely packed
101 titanium dioxide particles on top of densely packed silicon dioxide or carbide
102 nanoparticles can theoretically achieve 17 °C below ambient at night and 5 °C below
103 ambient under direct solar radiation. However, experiments conducted in Shanghai did
104 not achieve subambient temperatures due to high relative humidity [15]. A polymer-
105 coated fused (PDMS) silica mirror achieved radiative cooling below ambient air
106 temperature under direct sunlight of 8.2 °C [16]. Using periodic high and low index
107 layers a radiative cooling power of $100 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ was attained [17]. An optimized BN, SiC,
108 and SiO₂ gratings on top of a metal/dielectric multilayer structure reached a mean
109 cooling power of $55 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [18]. An equilibrium daytime temperature of -13 °C and a
110 cooling power of $105 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ was achieved with two thermally emitting photonic crystal
111 layers comprised of SiC and quartz, on top of a broadband solar reflector made of
112 three sets of five bilayers made of MgF₂ and TiO₂ with varying periods on a silver
113 substrate [19]. A complex structure of symmetrically shaped conical metamaterial
114 pillars composed of alternating layers of aluminum and germanium can reach a
115 daytime equilibrium temperature of 9 °C below the ambient temperature and 12 °C at
116 night [20].

117 Photonic materials sometimes include 3D volumes to improve and tune the emissivity
118 towards the desired spectrum. A cell consisting of a thick phosphorus-doped n-type
119 doped silicon substrate and two identical rectangular dielectric resonators numerically
120 achieved a nighttime minimum temperature decrease of 10.29 K at thermal equilibrium
121 and 7.36 K at daytime with a maximum net cooling power of $95.84 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [21]. An
122 experiment doped 25 μm thick polyethylene (PE) with SiC and SiO₂ nanoparticles on
123 top of aluminum, the device was covered with an IR transparent cover (10 μm PE) to
124 avoid convective heat gains achieving an actual stagnation temperature of 17 °C below
125 ambient in Sydney with about 3 mm of water vapor pressure [22].

126 Many radiative cooling materials have been developed using polymeric derived
127 composites. A glass-polymer hybrid material [23] achieved a cooling power of $93 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$
128 under direct sunshine at noon. The material's performance was tested in China
129 comparing two boxes (one with the material and the other without it) where the inside
130 air temperature was measured, showing a $21.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ difference between [24]. A cost-
131 effective double-layer coating embedded with titanium dioxide and black carbon
132 particles predicted a net cooling power of $100 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ during the day and $180 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ at
133 night [25]. Another test in Shanghai compared twelve samples of SiO_2 microsphere-
134 Poly-4-methyl-1-pentene (TPX) hybrid system deposited on fluorine doped tin oxide
135 (FTO) substrates showing temperatures about $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than a black surface, $12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
136 lower than the silver coated glass, and $8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than the FTO sample; however, they
137 did not achieve subambient cooling, showing an average temperature of $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ higher
138 than ambient.

139 Paints for easy and scalable application based on a hierarchically porous
140 poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropene) have achieved a subambient
141 temperature drop of $6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and cooling powers of $96 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [26]. A $7.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ subambient
142 temperature drop was reported at noontime in Beijing by spraying zinc phosphate
143 sodium onto aluminum [27]. Aperture dependency designs with shaded radiative
144 cooling surfaces were introduced by Trombe (cited by [28]) and continued by [28–31],
145 showing temperature drops of up to $11 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below ambient temperature.

146 Besides material development, several authors focused on system development [32–
147 39]. However, systems relying solely on fluid circulations are focused on nighttime
148 radiative cooling. A radiator insulated with polystyrene foam and bubbled plastic sheets
149 used as top cover achieved $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below ambient temperature without a heat source
150 and a plastic cover in Shiraz (Iran) [32]. Erell and Etzion tested a system based on
151 circulating water from a roof pond through a radiator system, the high water
152 temperature aided in the heat elimination from radiation and convection [33]. The same

153 authors tested a cheap, simple, and flexible design for a cooling radiator, achieving a
154 mean nightly cooling output of 90 W m^{-2} under typical desert meteorological conditions
155 in Israel. [34]. An unglazed radiator performed well in clear and low humidity nights in
156 Norway; nevertheless, the authors [35] suggested experimenting in climates with
157 cooling demand. Similar research conducted in Iran achieved an average net cooling
158 power of $45 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and lowered the water accumulation tank up to $8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [36]. A group of
159 Spanish researchers tested radiators with different infrared emissivities and achieved
160 average cooling powers of $60 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [37].

161 Recent research proposed a single-phase thermosiphon [38] for cold collection and
162 radiative cooling storage. Instead of using an electric pump, their device used
163 buoyancy force to drive heat transfer fluid and achieved an average cooling flux of 105
164 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ cooling flux. A daytime radiative cooling system was proposed in [39], where
165 series of panels cooled water up to $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below the ambient air temperature, covering
166 the panels with a visibly-reflective extruded copolymer mirror (3M Vikuiti ESR film).
167 Moreover, the authors modeled the panel integrated on the condenser side of a
168 building's cooling system in Las Vegas and calculated an electricity reduction of 21%
169 during the summer.

170 Systems that work at temperatures higher than the ambient present an advantage
171 since convective heat exchange increases the rate at which energy is removed from
172 the system rather than impede it. This feature of the system obviates the need for
173 windscreens [33]. Convective heat gains remain a problem to be solved. If subambient
174 temperatures are reached, the convection forces tend to augment the temperature of
175 the radiative cooler. According to Lu et al. [40], the convective heat transfer reduction
176 can be solved in two ways, with wind covers and windshields. The most researched
177 wind covers have been made of polyethylene [41–43]. However, its aging degradation
178 is a challenge to be solved [44]. When a thin layer of water precipitates directly on the
179 radiator, it improves its performance since water has a high emissivity. Nevertheless, it

180 reduces the transmittance when it is located on the cover and, therefore, the net output
181 thermal radiation [45]. Moreover, dust accumulation reduces the efficiency of radiator
182 systems that incorporate transparent windscreens [33]. Finally, radiative cooling
183 materials' optimal spectral characteristics depend on the climate conditions and the
184 type of application [46]. In that study, a series of daytime radiative cooling materials,
185 theoretical materials, and existing materials were simulated under a passive and active
186 approach in two differentiated climates, concluding that a material that performs well in
187 a dry climate as a passive solution could perform poorly as an active solution.

188 This research aims to study low-cost scalable DTRC materials for the built environment
189 under different meteorological conditions. The authors studied the performance of
190 several materials and compared them with the substrates without coatings. The
191 materials were tested in a moderate climate nearby Pamplona (Spain) Cfb according to
192 the Köppen-Geiger classification without a convection shield. This research's novelty is
193 the design, optimization, and testing –under different meteorological conditions– of
194 innovative low-cost and scalable daytime radiative cooling materials.

195

196 **2. Methodology**

197 This research focuses on developing and testing scalable daytime radiative cooling
198 materials for future application in the built environment based on a reflective substrate
199 and an emissive layer. First, different types of multilayer materials were studied and
200 compared as candidates to enhance the radiative cooling surfaces' emissivity in the
201 atmospheric transparency window for applications as built environment coatings. The
202 design of these multilayer structures' parameters was done considering industry
203 fabrication capabilities for film deposition, and then, the dimensions of each design
204 were analyzed to obtain maximum absorption from 8 to 13 μm . After the materials and
205 the structure design compositions were selected (SiO_2 as emissive layer and aluminum
206 as substrate), a series of numerical optimizations were made to determine each layer's

207 ideal thickness. Secondly, a systematic process based on computer simulation using
208 the CST Studio Suite [47], a commercial code based on the Finite Integration time-
209 domain Technique (FIT), was developed to determine the emissivity response of the
210 analyzed samples. Moreover, the optical response in the visible range was
211 simultaneously calculated and analyzed to evaluate the proposed structures' effect in
212 the reflected and transmitted power. Afterward, the materials were fabricated and
213 characterized in the visible and infrared wavelengths. Finally, the samples were tested
214 under non-ideal outdoor conditions.

215 **2.1. Material selection and design**

216 The research takes after the approach proposed in [48,49], which includes a reflective
217 substrate and an emissive coating. Therefore, the selected materials for optimization
218 are silica and aluminum. Silica is transparent in the visible range presenting a refractive
219 index almost constant of 1.4. The transmittance of silica is high until 2.5 μm ; from that
220 wavelength onwards, silica is almost opaque, its absorption rises strongly, and the
221 transmitted power can be considered zero. Therefore, silica presents a significantly
222 different refractive index in the visible region and the atmospheric window (AW) (8 to
223 13 μm), influenced by the vibrational modes of oxygen atoms [55]. The excitation of
224 these vibrational modes by infrared (IR) radiation is macroscopically observed as
225 absorption bands in the IR spectrum at 9 and 20 μm [57].

226 When calculating a silica layer's absorption, we find two different situations depending
227 on the layer thickness. When the layer thickness is greater than the incident
228 wavelength, most of the energy is absorbed by the material at the atmospheric window
229 wavelengths. However, silica layers with a thickness smaller than the IR light
230 wavelength transmit radiation for all wavelengths except for the abovementioned
231 bands. Therefore, strong absorption is obtained using thin silica layers in narrow
232 spectral regions centered at 9 and 20 μm .

233 Aluminum reflectance is higher than 90% from near UV to mid-IR except for a sharp dip
234 at 0.8 μm . The best reflectance aluminum performance is obtained from mid-IR (2 μm),
235 making it an excellent lossy reflector in the thermal wavelength range. Aluminum slowly
236 oxidizes, resulting in a reduction of reflectance. Therefore, aluminum must include a
237 protective dielectric overcoat that prevents oxidation.

238 **2.2. Optimization**

239 The design parameters of these multilayer structures were chosen considering industry
240 fabrication capabilities for film deposition. Each design's dimensions were analyzed to
241 obtain maximum absorption in the AW (8 to 13 μm). A systematic process based on
242 computer simulation was developed to determine the analyzed samples'
243 emissivity/absorptivity response. Moreover, the optical response in the visible range
244 was simultaneously calculated and analyzed to evaluate the proposed structures' effect
245 in the reflected and transmitted power. The target was to obtain the highest reflectivity
246 in the solar wavelengths and the highest emissivity possible in the atmospheric
247 window. Simulations in the thermal wavelength range (8–13 μm) were carried out using
248 the CST Studio Suite, based on FIT [50]. FIT is a consistent discretization scheme that
249 provides a reformulation of Maxwell's equations in their integral form suitable for
250 computers, and it allows to simulate electromagnetic field problems with complex
251 geometries and materials. This program is an electromagnetic field simulation software
252 package especially suited for analysis and design in the microwave, terahertz, and
253 optical range.

254 In order to calculate the absorptivity of the structures in the visible and NIR ranges, we
255 used Grating Diffraction Calculator (GD-Calc) code [51], a commercial software
256 package developed by Kenneth C. Johnson and integrated into Matlab that uses
257 rigorously coupled-wave analysis (RCWA) [52]. GD-Calc resolves the Maxwell
258 equations for a single frequency and analyzes the weight of each diffraction order
259 separately in the power balance. A summation of the power density in all diffraction

260 orders provides the reflection and transmission values, obtaining the absorption. GD-
261 Calc's properties resolve the meshing problems in the visible range of CST for large-
262 sized samples since it is possible to simulate structures much larger than the shorter
263 wavelength of the calculation in a reasonable period [53].

264 The composition of aluminum with an emissive layer of SiO_2 was simulated. As is
265 shown in Figure 1, the thicker the silica coating is, the more emissive it is in the AW.
266 On the other hand, the increasing thickness does not increase the emissivity on the
267 solar wavelengths.

268

269 *Figure 1: Radiative cooling material: emissivity calculations for aluminum with different thicknesses of*
270 *SiO_2 .*

271 A layer of silver was included to improve the reflectivity in the solar wavelength range.
272 Two thickness values were simulated, 100 nm and 200 nm. The result in Figure 2,
273 compares the reflectivity with the same structure without the silver coating. Both silver
274 thicknesses result in the same optical behavior (dashed grey line and solid red line are
275 identical). As shown in the figure, the material without the silver coating (solid black
276 line) is less reflective in the solar wavelengths and its average emissivity is higher
277 without silver. Moreover, the emissivity is significantly reduced from 0.5 μm onwards
278 using a silver layer, enhancing the range's reflectivity.

279

280 *Figure 2: Emissivity simulation of an aluminum substrate with different thicknesses of silver and 2 μm of*
 281 *SiO₂: no silver (solid black line), 0.1 μm (dashed grey line), and 0.2 μm (solid red line).*

282 2.3. Development

283 Several deposition technique options were researched, such as plasma-enhanced
 284 chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) and sputtering; however, since the deposition's
 285 scalability was a requisite, spray coating was chosen. As a result of choosing this
 286 deposition method, instead of working with SiO₂ as a bulk material, a silica derived
 287 polymer, polymethylsilsesquioxane (PMSQ), was chosen to be applied on the
 288 substrate. The simulation study established the importance of having two layers
 289 (reflective and absorptive) and the required thickness's magnitude to obtain their
 290 optimal characteristics.

291 The emissive layer was fabricated by L'Urederra Technological Center using 20 nm
 292 silica SiO₂ nanoparticles embedded at a 5% weight in a PMSQ matrix. The aluminum
 293 substrate finish was a mirror polished, alloy 1050A H18, which is the most reflective on
 294 the market. Nevertheless, once its reflectivity was measured, it was lower than the
 295 theoretical maximum (Figure 3). Therefore, 3M Vikuiti Enhanced Solar Reflector [54]
 296 was an alternative substrate to aluminum, used previously in two works [39,55]. As

297 seen in Figure 2, adding a nanolayer of silver would increase its solar reflectivity;
298 however, it would lead to higher costs and scalability and therefore was dismissed.

299

300 *Figure 3: Solar reflectivity simulation of the aluminum substrate (solid black line) vs. theoretical aluminum*
301 *(dashed black line) [56].*

302 Although the final product differed from the one designed and optimized in subsection
303 2.2, unfortunately, no new optimizations could be carried out since the emissive layer's
304 exact complex refractive index is a prerequisite for simulating. To measure the
305 refractive index, several universities and research centers were contacted. However,
306 they could not characterize the complex index due to the impossibility of measuring
307 rough samples in the mid-infrared (2 to 20 μm). The refractive index measurement
308 requires perfectly planar specular surfaces and is usually measured with an
309 ellipsometer from 200 to 1500 nm and a spectrophotometer for the infrared. If the
310 samples are rough, as in this case, complex models specifically developed are used
311 and require several different measurements (diffuse reflectance in the solid sample and
312 powder absorption). The second alternative to optimize the thickness was to use
313 information from the literature, but the complex index of PMSQ was not available in the
314 literature as far as the authors know. Hence, the materials could not be optimized with
315 the real refractive indexes.

316 The samples were developed using spray deposition on top of squares samples of 200
 317 by 200 mm of two different materials: aluminum and Vikuiti ESR films (Figure 4). The
 318 substrates were washed with ethanol paper to clean the surface from impurities,
 319 allowing a correct deposition of the emissive layer. Depending on the substrate's
 320 nature, metallic or plastic, two different emissive layers were applied (Figure 5).

321

322 *Figure 4: Configuration of the different fabricated samples. A stands for the aluminum substrate, AS for the*
 323 *aluminum plus the emissive layer, V for Vikuiti, and VS for Vikuiti plus the emissive layer.*

324

325 *Figure 5: Spray coating onto (a) metallic substrate and (b) plastic substrate.*

326 The metallic samples were curated for an hour on a stove at 200 °C. Nevertheless, the
 327 samples with a plastic substrate did not have a post-application treatment, and the
 328 emissive layer was curated at ambient temperature. The aluminum samples were

329 applied changing the deposition speed and quantity to achieve a layer of approximately
330 1 μm . Target thickness was 10 μm , but due to viscosity restrictions of deposition, the
331 maximum deposited thickness was 3.7 μm . The Vikuiti substrates received two and
332 three layers of the emissive coating to achieve the minimum 1 μm target.

333 **2.4. Characterization**

334 The reflectance was characterized in the visible and near-infrared spectra (from 200 to
335 1100 nm), using a combined Deuterium Halogen light source (Top Sensor System DH-
336 2000-S) with an integrating sphere and a CCD spectrometer (OceanOptics USB2000-
337 FLG) with an unpolarized light source and a calibrated high specular reflectance
338 standard. A Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (Bruker Vertex 80V) equipped with
339 an infrared microscope (Hyperion 3000) was employed to perform measurements in
340 the near-infrared (NIR, 0.78-2.5 μm) and mid-infrared (MIR, 2.5-25 μm). The excitation
341 was done with unpolarized light sources (halogen lamp in the NIR and a Globar source
342 in the MIR) and the detection with an InGaAs detector (NIR) and a nitrogen cooled
343 MCT detector (MIR). The cooler's reflectance was characterized in normal reflection
344 with a gold mirror used as a reflectance standard. Besides the emissivity and
345 reflectivity measurements, all samples had their coating thickness, adherence, gloss,
346 and hardness characterized.

347 **2.5. Experimental setup**

348 The performance of the materials was compared to the substrates without any coating.
349 The samples were contained in hollowed-out squares in an extruded polystyrene (XPS)
350 board to eliminate heat conduction; this condition can be considered almost adiabatic.
351 The experiment was conducted from October 16 to 20 of 2020 (Day 1 to Day 5) on the
352 National Renewable Energy Center (CENER) rooftop, as is shown in Figure 7.
353 Meteorological data was recorded using CENER's equipment throughout the duration
354 of the experiment. The station is composed of 3 pyranometers for global horizontal
355 irradiance (Kipp&Zonen, CMP22), 1 shaded pyranometer for diffuse radiance

356 (Kipp&Zonnen, CMP22), 1 pyrhelimeter on a sun tracker for beam irradiance
357 (Kipp&Zonnen, CHP1), and a shaded pyrgeometer for downwelling infrared radiation
358 (Kipp&Zonnen, CGR4). Kipp & Zonen equipment maximum uncertainty is 2% for hourly
359 totals and 1% for daily totals. Other components are sensors to measure atmospheric
360 pressure (Vaisala, PTB110), air temperature and relative humidity (Vaisala, HMP45C),
361 and wind speed with an anemometer (Ammonit, P6100H). The air temperature
362 measurements range from -39.2 °C to +60 °C, the accuracy at 20 °C is ± 0.2 °C. The
363 relative humidity measurement range is 0.8 to 100 °C with accuracy at 20 °C against
364 factory references ± 1 %RH. The anemometer range is 0.3 to 75 ms^{-1} , and ± 0.03 ms^{-1}
365 accuracy, and the wind vane has a full 360° range, $\pm 2^\circ$ accuracy, and 0.5° resolution.

366 This data was used to characterize the outdoor climatic conditions onsite. The
367 measurement is based on the thermal balance of the material. The surface
368 temperature when exposed to the direct sun complemented with the meteorological
369 data is needed for testing material's thermal performance. The six samples' surface
370 temperature was monitored with six surface temperature sensors (thermocouples type
371 K connector TP from Testo) connected to 3 data logging devices (Testo Saveris 2-T3
372 WiFi) with $\pm (0.5 + 0.5 \%$ of mv) °C accuracy and range is -40 °C to 400 °C with ± 0.2
373 °C accuracy. As seen in Figure 7, a cell phone connected to a battery was placed to
374 generate a WiFi net to retrieve data from the dataloggers and synchronize it with the
375 cloud.

376

377 *Figure 6: Photos of the experimental setup in CENER, Sarriguren, Spain. The samples are contained in an*
 378 *XPS board and monitored with thermocouples connected to dataloggers.*

379 The following equations describe the experiment's thermal balance.

$$P_{out} = \varepsilon_s \cdot \sigma \cdot T_{sample}^4 \quad (1)$$

380 Where P_{out} is the outgoing radiating power ε_s is the emissivity of the surface the
 381 blackbody radiation in the wavenumber ν when its temperature is T_s , $G_s(\nu)$ the
 382 irradiance received by the surface at a wavenumber ν .

$$P_{in} = R_{solar} + (h_{conv} + h_{cond}) \cdot (T_{amb} - T_{sample}) + R_{amb} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta T = (P_{in} - P_{out})/A_{surface} \quad (3)$$

383

384

385 *Figure 7: Photos of the experimental setup (a) 3 Wi-Fi dataloggers (2 thermocouples each), Wi-Fi-net*
 386 *created with a smartphone plugged into a power bank to allow remote monitoring during several days, (b)*
 387 *the thermocouple is attached with thermal paste to the samples' bottom side with conductive paste.*

388 **3. Results**

389 **3.1. Samples and characterization**

390 Two types of radiative cooling materials were developed, based on an aluminum
 391 metallic substrate and a plastic substrate, summarized in Table 1. The following
 392 samples are tested, a bare aluminum substrate (A), the Vikuiti sample (V), 2 DTRC
 393 materials of aluminum with the silica emissive layer (AS1 and AS2), and 2 two samples
 394 of the emissive layer formulated for plastic deposition on top of a Vikuiti film (VS1 and
 395 VS2).

396 *Table 1: Summary of the developed samples. S stands for substrates and DTRC for Daytime Radiative*
 397 *cooling materials. A is the aluminum substrate, AS the aluminum plus the emissive layer, V is Vikuiti, and*
 398 *VS is the Vikuiti substrate plus the emissive layer.*

	Substrate		Emissive layer		
	Sample code	Material	Material	Thickness	Mass
S	A	Al (1 mm)	-	-	-
	V	Vikuiti ESR	-	-	-
DTRC	AS1	Al (1 mm)	PMSQ	1.5 ± 0.6 μm	13.3 mg
	AS2			2.2 ± 0.4 μm	22.5 mg

Sample code	Substrate		Emissive layer	
	Material	Material	Thickness	Mass
		+		
		nanoparticles		
		SiO ₂		
VS1		Plastic PMSQ		17.4 mg
		+		
VS2	Vikuiti ESR	nanoparticles	-	36.6 mg
		SiO ₂		

399

400

401 *Figure 8: Photo of the samples indicated in Table 1, from left to right: aluminum with an emissive coating*
 402 *(AS1), Vikuiti Substrate (V), and two samples with the emissive layer on Vikuiti ESR (VS1 and VS2).*

403 As shown in Figure 9(a) and Figure 10(a), the reflectivity in the samples' optical range
 404 with aluminum and Vikuiti ESR substrates is significantly different. The commercial
 405 substrate (Vikuiti) presents a reflectivity close to 1 for all the analyzed samples,
 406 including the samples with the emissive layer. In contrast, the aluminum substrate
 407 shows a reflectivity of 0.7, 30% lower than Vikuiti, lowering up to 0.6 when the emissive
 408 coating is applied (Figure 9(a), red solid and blue dashed lines). The previous result
 409 suggests that emissivity increased, as shown in Figure 9 (b), from 0.3 to 0.4. On the
 410 other hand, observing the coatings' effect in the atmospheric window (Figure 9(b) and
 411 Figure 10(b)), coating increases the total emissivity in the range 8-13 μm for both
 412 cases. The emissive coat (Figure 9(b)) enhances the emissivity at 10 μm from 0.04 to
 413 0.45 and 0.7 for the samples AS1 and AS2, respectively. It is important to note that the

414 abovementioned emissivity peak appears by the effect of the silica particles. In the
 415 atmospheric window, A shows 3.3% emissivity; the application of the coating increases
 416 the emissivity value by 24% for AS1 and 32.9% for AS2. In V's case, the AW's
 417 emissivity is 85.8% increasing by 9% for VS1 and 1% for VS2. This result agrees with
 418 the numerical calculations of silica films with a thickness of around 1 μm shown in
 419 Figure 1. The simulations' main differences are especially significant in the emissivity
 420 value at 13 μm wavelength due to the PMSQ matrix where the silica particles are
 421 embedded (Figure 11). In the case of Vikuiti ESR substrate, the effect of the PMSQ
 422 enhances emissivity by 10% in the IR range compared to the bare sample. In contrast,
 423 the layer's effect is almost constant from 1 to 17 μm obtaining a broadband emissivity
 424 response.

425 As mentioned before in 2.3, the simulations and optimizations were conducted with
 426 ideal and bulk materials, whose refractive indexes were obtained from databases and
 427 literature. The differences between simulated and measured emissivity are due to the
 428 final materials used. silica derived polymer, PMSQ, was employed instead of using bulk
 429 SiO₂ films. Which has a different effective refractive index from silica. Nevertheless,
 430 the simulations validated the proposed structure and gave a better understanding of
 431 the structures' optical behavior. Moreover, they provided useful information regarding
 432 the appropriate emissive material's thickness.

433

434 Figure 9: Measured (a) optical reflectivity and (b) IR Emissivity of the samples with aluminum substrate (A),
 435 and two samples of aluminum with emissive coating, AS1 and AS2.

436

437 Figure 10: Measured (a) optical reflectivity and (b) IR Emissivity of the samples with Vikuiti ESR substrate
 438 (V), V bare Vikuiti substrate, and two samples with emissive coating, VS1 and VS2.

439

440 Figure 11: Emissivity comparison between the developed aluminum and PMSQ samples (AS1 and AS2)
 441 and the simulated aluminum and SiO₂ samples (Simulated AS).

442 As mentioned above, a comprehensive characterization was performed, where the
 443 samples' reflectivity and emissivity, the coating thickness, hardness, and gloss were
 444 measured, as seen in Table 2. Once the emissive coating was applied to the aluminum

445 samples, the gloss was reduced significantly. On the contrary, little difference was seen
 446 in the Vikuiti samples.

447 *Table 2: Sample's characterization: gloss, hardness, and the number of layers of emissive coatings.*

	Sample code	Gloss 60°	Hardness	Number of layers of emissive coating
S	A	721 ± 6	<9B	-
	V	1001 ± 2	-	-
DTRC	AS1	437 ± 23	H	1 layer slow speed application
	AS2	465 ± 34	F	2 layers regular speed application
	VS1	997 ± 7	-	2
	VS1	992 ± 4	-	3

448

449 The proposed emissive layer has an approximate cost of 0.3 €/m for a layer of 2 µm of
 450 PMSQ and SiO₂ nanoparticles, being competitive for built-environment applications.

451 **3.2. Experiment**

452

453 *Figure 12: Photos of the experimental setup, (a) Day 1: sunny day, and (b) Day 5: rainy day.*

454 The experiment conducted in the National Renewable Energy Center (CENER) rooftop
 455 allowed the samples' direct exposure to the sky without unobstructed views since the

456 facility is designed to test solar photovoltaic and thermal panels (Figure 12). A total of 6
457 samples from Table 1 were tested, the bare aluminum substrate (A), the Vikuiti sample
458 (V), 2 DTRC materials of aluminum with the silica emissive layer (AS1 and AS2), and 2
459 two samples the emissive layer formulated for plastic deposition on top of a Vikuiti film
460 (VS1 and VS2). The experiment was monitored for five consecutive days with different
461 meteorological conditions. Figure 13 shows the meteorological data from those five
462 days.

463 The samples' surface temperature was recorded and compared to the ambient air
464 temperature in Figure 14. By noon, all the samples achieved subambient cooling even
465 with an incident solar radiation of $633 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and infrared atmospheric radiation ranging
466 from 280 to $320 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. The higher ambient temperatures induced by the solar radiation
467 heated the samples. Before noon, the aluminum sample A was up to $3.62 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below
468 ambient, the samples with the emissive coating, AS1 and AS2, achieved $3.62 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and
469 $3.92 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The samples with the commercial substrate, V, V1, and V2, had
470 a higher solar reflectivity and achieved $6.12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $7.32 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and $7.12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ below ambient
471 temperature. From 12:55 onwards, the samples with the aluminum substrate were
472 hotter than the ambient air temperature due to the high absorption of solar radiation in
473 the $0.3\text{-}2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ range. Nevertheless, the AS samples were up to $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ cooler than the
474 aluminum sample and an average of $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than the sample without coating. The
475 materials with coating showed a better behavior due their ability to radiate heat in the
476 infrared wavelengths. The Vikuiti samples' low surface temperature led to surface water
477 condensations, as seen in Figure 16. These samples had an almost ideal solar
478 reflectivity and a broadband emissivity in the infrared wavelengths since the materials
479 reflected all the incident heat and emitted any possible heat gains, leading to
480 substantial temperature drops.

481

482 *Figure 13: Climate data during the five consecutive days of the experiment.*

483

484 *Figure 14: Samples surface temperature throughout the five days of the experiment.*

485 The materials presented three distinct behaviors (Figure 13) corresponding to different
 486 climatic conditions (Figure 14). Day 1 was sunny with low temperature (mean of 10.5
 487 °C day and 4°C at night) and high humidity (62%), the aluminum samples heated up
 488 during the day and attained subambient cooling at night; the same happened with the V
 489 samples. The aluminum samples behaved better than on any other day, as discussed
 490 in [57], the cooling performance of the materials has an almost linear response to
 491 changes in the ambient air temperature.

492 Day 2 and 3 were similar, sunny with high passing clouds, moderate daytime
493 temperature (mean of 15 °C day and 7 °C at night), medium relative humidity (55%)
494 and low wind speeds ($0.78 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$); as a result, all the samples had a similar thermal
495 response both days. Day 2 had a slightly higher relative humidity than day 3, translated
496 into lower temperatures during day 2 and higher during day 3. The aluminum samples
497 heated up more significantly than the previous days due to higher temperatures and
498 similar relative humidity. The plastic samples achieved subambient cooling during both
499 days (Figure 14 (b)) since the relatively low humidity favors the thermal exchange. In
500 cloudy days, broadband emitters end up absorbing radiation coming from the clouds,
501 and as a result, the thermal equilibrium is achieved at higher temperatures.

502 Finally, day 4 was very sunny during daytime and very cloudy at night with high
503 temperatures, 20.6 °C during the day and 18 °C at night, and low relative humidity
504 (39%) and higher ambient radiation ($323 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$). Although the temperatures reached
505 up to 22.3 °C during the day and were higher than the previous days, the aluminum
506 samples were cooler, 9 °C (AS1 and AS2) over ambient temperature. Outgoing
507 radiation evacuated from the materials was favored by low relative humidity. On the
508 contrary, in the previous days, as seen in Figure 14 (a), AS1 and AS2 had reached 18
509 °C above ambient (day 2 and day 3) since water vapor inhibits outgoing radiation. The
510 V samples achieved higher temperatures than in the previous days and surpassed
511 ambient temperature. This phenomenon might be explained because the longwave
512 radiation increases from noon onwards and lower wind speeds, making the convective
513 heat exchange lower, penalizing the broadband emitters (VS1 and VS2) while
514 benefitting the strictly spectrally selective materials (AS1 and AS2). When surfaces are
515 above ambient air temperature, wind helps to reduce the surface temperature. The
516 night leading to day 5 was cloudy with higher longwave radiation (Figure 13 (a)); thus,
517 the samples did not cool down as much as in the previous days. Moreover, on day 4,

518 higher convection led the Vikuiti samples below ambient air temperature to increase
519 their temperature around and above ambient air temperature.

520 Finally, to see the emissive coating effect, the samples' surface temperature was
521 compared to the bare substrate in Figure 15. Although AS1 had a lower solar
522 reflectivity and lower emissivity in the transparency window than AS2 (see Figure 9),
523 which is considered a worse optical behavior, it performed better throughout all the
524 days, as seen in Figure 15 (a). This behavior might be related to high relative humidity
525 values. V samples are broadband emitters in the infrared wavelengths (Figure 10), V
526 and V2 had a very similar response, and V1 emissivity was higher. Nevertheless, V2
527 achieved more punctual temperature drops than V1, but it was V1 that achieved a
528 more stable lower temperature during all the experiment days except day 1, probably
529 due to low temperatures and high humidity (Figure 15 (b)). Several significant
530 temperature drops in the AS samples (Figure 15 (a)) can be explained because of
531 water condensation on the samples' surface before noon. Water condensation
532 augments emissivity, and the evaporation of this layer might lead to some significant
533 temperature decrease due to evaporative cooling. Although the temperature difference
534 is less significant, it can be observed in the Vikuiti samples around noon.

535

536 *Figure 15: DTRC sample's surface temperature difference with the bare substrates (a) comparison of AS1*

537 *and AS2 with bare aluminum (A) (b) comparison of V1 and V2 with bare Vikuiti substrate (V). Negative*

538 *values reflect when the samples with coating are below the substrate's temperature.*

539

540 *Figure 16: Photos taken Day 4 at 12:12 (a) all the samples in the insulation board, showing condensation*
 541 *in the samples with the plastic substrate (b) the Vikuiti samples with the emissive coating.*

542 Table 3 to Table 7 summarize the surface's maximum and minimum temperatures, the
 543 maximum and minimum difference between surface temperature and ambient
 544 temperature. Positive values correspond to materials heating and negative values
 545 when materials cool down below ambient temperatures.

546 *Table 3: Summary of the measured surface temperature, data from day 1.*

Day 1 (11:00-24:00)						
	A	AS1	AS2	V	V1	V2
Max surface T	23.2	21.6	21.9	15	15	13.7
(°C) ±0.2 °C						
Min surface T (°C)	0.2	-0.6	0.2	-1.2	-1.5	-1.2
±0.2 °C						
ΔT Max (T_{surf}-	11.86	9.86	10.46	3.92	3.94	2.52
T_{amb}) ±0.4 °C						
ΔT Min (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	-3.43	-4.41	-3.71	-5.73	-5.83	-6.13
±0.4 °C						

547

548 *Table 4: Summary of the measured surface temperature, data from day 2.*

Day 2 (00:00-24:00)						
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	A	AS1	AS2	V	V1	V2
Max surface T	33.5	30.6	31.6	16.1	15.5	16.2
(°C) ±0.2 °C						
Min surface T (°C)	5.3	2.8	3.8	2	1.1	1.4
±0.2 °C						
ΔT Max (T_{surf}-	18.15	15.37	15.94	1.88	0.53	1.20
T_{amb}) ±0.4 °C						
ΔT Min (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	-2.96	-3.37	-2.66	-5.83	-6.63	-5.97
±0.4 °C						

549

550 *Table 5: Summary of the measured surface temperature, data from day 3.*

Day 3 (00:00-24:00)						
	A	AS1	AS2	V	V1	V2
Max surface T	36.5	34.2	34.6	16.8	15.8	17.2
(°C) ±0.2 °C						
Min surface T (°C)	7.6	6.4	6.6	4.1	3.1	3.3
±0.2 °C						
ΔT Max (T_{surf}-	17.47	15.17	15.21	1.28	-0.10	0.43
T_{amb}) ±0.4 °C						
ΔT Min (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	-6.49	-6.63	-6.63	-8.23	-9.13	-9.13
±0.4 °C						

551

552 *Table 6: Summary of the measured surface temperature, data from day 4.*

Day 4 (00:00-24:00)						
	A	AS1	AS2	V	V1	V2
Max surface T	33.4	32.1	31.6	25.3	24.2	23.5
(°C) ±0.2 °C						

Min surface T (°C)	17	11.9	13.2	11.5	9.7	9.9
±0.2 °C						
ΔT Max (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	11.23	9.93	9.43	3.75	2.55	1.84
±0.4 °C						
ΔT Min (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	-1.36	-7.21	-5.91	-8.31	-10.11	-7.21
±0.4 °C						

553

554 *Table 7: Summary of measured surface temperature, data from day 5.*

Day 5 (00:00-09:25)						
	A	AS1	AS2	V	V1	V2
Max surface T (°C)	18.2	17.9	17.9	17.2	16.8	17.3
±0.2 °C						
Min surface T (°C)	12.9	12.7	13	13.1	13	12.9
±0.2 °C						
ΔT Max (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	0.84	0.55	0.55	0.29	-0.45	-0.06
±0.4 °C						
ΔT Min (T_{surf}-T_{amb})	-3.40	-3.57	-3.40	-3.31	-3.81	-3.70
±0.4 °C						

555

556 **3.3. Discussion of the results**

557 This research has studied scalable daytime radiative cooling materials in a moderate
558 climate throughout different meteorological conditions far from the usual experiments
559 done under ideal settings (no convection and low relative humidity). This study
560 presents the simulation, development, characterization, and testing of two kinds of
561 daytime radiative cooling materials based on silica-derived emissive layers. The
562 material design and simulation proved to be a valuable tool while leading to an in-depth
563 understanding of the structures' optical behavior. The optimization provided the
564 necessary insight regarding the adequate material's thickness and validated the

565 proposed structures before fabrication. The sprayable emissive coating is a highly
566 versatile solution for plastic and metallic applications; it is transparent in the solar
567 wavelengths leaving the substrate exposed; thus, the final material's solar reflectivity
568 depends on the substrate of application. Two kinds of reflective layers were selected,
569 aluminum substrate and commercial Vikuiti. The simulations and the finally employed
570 materials differ due to limitations in the fabrication process. Since the bare aluminum
571 substrate's reflectivity is lower than developed materials that were neither very solar
572 reflective nor very emissive in the atmospheric window, another substrate was selected
573 to improve the solar wavelengths' reflectivity Vikuiti. As a result, a new formulation for
574 plastic applications was developed. Their reflectivity, gloss, adherence, among others,
575 were characterized.

576 The metallic samples resulted in spectrally selective daytime radiative cooling (DTRC)
577 materials in the atmospheric window, and the plastic samples were broadband
578 emitters. The experiment presents a comprehensive overview of their true potential
579 throughout different meteorological conditions, wind speed, humidity, temperature, and
580 ambient radiation. The materials with a highly reflective substrate such as Vikuiti can
581 achieve subambient cooling during the day, however under high ambient radiation and
582 relative humidity perform poorly; therefore, strict selectivity is desired. The more strictly
583 selective materials based on aluminum (AS) are absorbent in the first atmospheric
584 window (8-13 μm); thus, the effect of the second atmospheric window (16–25 μm) is
585 negligible. The V and VS samples are broadband emitters, and any received longwave
586 radiation will affect them by increasing the thermal balance temperature. In this case,
587 the second atmospheric window will have a more significant impact. Both atmospheric
588 windows are affected by humidity, affecting more the broadband materials. Although
589 the samples with the metallic substrate are above ambient air temperature throughout
590 most of the daytime, the addition of an emissive layer improves its emissivity

591 considerably and, therefore, its thermal behavior during the day, compared to the
592 substrate.

593 The spray deposition used in this research presents two main advantages: speed and
594 scalability. Drawbacks from this technique are thickness control and replicability.
595 Deposition with this fabrication technique should be further studied. As mentioned
596 before, the thicknesses could not be controlled as desired, leading to two
597 consequences. First, every time a deposition is made, the thickness will be different,
598 leading to a replicability problem. Secondly, the spray coating is done manually,
599 leading to heterogeneous deposition in the samples. Concluding, the deposition
600 method needs substantial changes, with a more mechanical and controlled process. It
601 is essential to control both the application homogeneity and thickness without
602 compromising the ability to scale the samples' size.

603 The experiment took place in Sarriguren, 8 km away from Pamplona during five
604 consecutive fall days (16th to October 20, 2020); according to the Köppen-Geiger
605 classification, it is a Cfb climate. To test the emissive coating's efficiency, the samples
606 without the coatings were tested alongside bare aluminum and one Vikuiti film (A and
607 V). The Vikuiti based samples V, V1 and V2 dropped their temperature during daytime
608 (12:00-15:00) an average of 1 °C, 2.05 °C and 2.70 °C below ambient, respectively,
609 and a maximum of 6.26 °C, 7.45 °C and, 7.97 °C. The samples with the aluminum
610 substrate did not reach subambient cooling during the entire day; however, the
611 temperature of the emissive coating samples was below the temperature of the bare
612 aluminum substrate, a mean of 1.88 °C (AS1) and 1.16 °C (AS2). All the samples
613 achieved nighttime radiative cooling since they were emissive in the atmospheric
614 window. The samples made of aluminum plus the emissive coating achieved a 1.88 °C
615 reduction compared to the bare aluminum and a maximum temperature difference of
616 11.2 °C (Day 3 at 12:55).

617 Other radiative cooling materials have been tested and proven subambient
618 temperatures, but either the relative humidity was lower, or a convection barrier
619 protected the samples, and in some instances, the sun was blocked with sun shading
620 devices. Raman et al. photonic structure reported a 4.9 K below ambient in Stanford;
621 the sample was protected with a polyethylene cover to eliminate convection [13].
622 Radiative cooling materials based on TiO_2 , SiO_2 , and SiC nanoparticles were tested in
623 Shanghai, Cfa climate humid subtropical. However, the materials did not achieve
624 subambient temperatures during the day due to high relative humidity (50-70%) [15].
625 Another test compared, in the same location, twelve samples of SiO_2 (TPX) hybrid
626 system deposited on fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrates, showing an average
627 temperature of 15 °C higher than ambient even with a convection barrier [58]. A
628 multilayer photonic material based on TiO_2 and SiO_2 reported a 7.3 °C subambient
629 temperature at noontime in Beijing with exceeding solar radiation of $430 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and
630 relative humidity between 50-90%. That material had a low-density polyethylene as a
631 wind cover [27], and a sun shading device was used. The results presented in this
632 study show a promising path in using PMSQ (polymethylsilsesquioxane) with silica
633 nanoparticles as an emissive coating for radiative cooling under various meteorological
634 conditions, where other experiments and materials failed to achieve subambient
635 cooling. The Vikuiti samples with the emissive coating achieved temperature reductions
636 up to 7.97 °C. Moreover, the easy deposition technique and the possibility to apply onto
637 other substrates present a great candidate for scalable daytime radiative cooling.
638 Finally, the materials were tested under non-favorable conditions, without sun shading
639 devices nor convective shields, achieving substantial temperature drops. The results
640 presented open an interesting research line for future application in the built
641 environment.

642

643 **4. Conclusions**

644 This research has studied scalable daytime radiative cooling materials in a moderate
645 climate throughout different meteorological conditions far from the usual experiments
646 done under real conditions and ideal setting (minimizing convection and relative
647 humidity). This study presents the simulation, development, characterization, and
648 testing of two kinds of daytime radiative cooling materials based on silica derived
649 emissive layers. The material design and simulation helped understand the structures'
650 optical behavior, providing the necessary insight to tailor the material's thickness and
651 validate the proposed structures before fabrication.

652 We have proved, for the first time to our knowledge, that low cost (0.3 €/m² for a layer
653 of 2 μm of PMSQ and SiO₂ particles), scalable and sprayable coatings provide
654 significant radiative cooling, as to reduce its temperature significantly over bare
655 substrates in real climatic conditions.

656 The following conclusions can be obtained:

657 (1) Under most climatic conditions, the materials have the ability to cool down a
658 metallic substrate a mean of at least 1.7 °C with up to 12 °C temperature drops.

659 (2) The samples based on Vikuiti dropped their temperature during the highest
660 solar radiation and maximum ambient temperatures, an average of 2.70 °C
661 below ambient and a maximum 7.97 °C during the day.

662 (3) The substrates presented (enhanced solar reflector ESR and aluminum), in
663 both cases, have better thermal behavior than the materials without treatment.

664 (4) Although the materials' spectra were not ideal 0.7 (solar reflectivity) and 0.34
665 (emissivity in the AW), the materials could stay below the ambient temperature
666 at least until noon.

667 (5) The cost and deposition system presented are good candidates for future broad
668 application in the built environment and architecture.

669 The path has proven promising for future scalable material development. Further
670 testing on sprayed coating techniques should be made:

671 (1) Applying on different substrates present in the built environment (e.g.,
672 concrete, ceramic, and glass). The potential substrates need to have sky
673 access to evacuate heat—especially important applications in roofs and other
674 exposed horizontal building surfaces.

675 (2) Testing under different meteorological conditions to determine the ideal material
676 for each climate and application.

677 (3) Incorporating low-cost switchable technologies to avoid overcooling during the
678 heating seasons.

679 (4) Studying their degradation and aging as they will be exposed to extreme
680 weather conditions and prolonged periods.

681 These new scalable polymeric materials could lower the cooling demands of buildings
682 and alleviate heat buildup in cities, aiding to lowering the Urban Heat Island
683 phenomenon. Moreover, the technique might be of significant interest for building
684 retrofitting as a spraying technique can be applied onsite or as industrialized elements.

685

686 **5. Declaration of interest**

687 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
688 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

689

690 **6. Contribution**

691 Laura Carlosena, investigation, conceptualization, methodology, data curation, formal
692 analysis, and writing original draft; Ángel Andueza, validation and software, writing,
693 reviewing, and editing; Luis Torres, data curation, reviewing and editing; Olatz Irulegi,
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697

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706

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